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ABSTRACTS

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Building a programmable, acoustically inducible Escherichia coli cell culture to test growth, viability, protein production yield and gene expression using a soundproof bacterial incubator

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Abstract: Among the various expression systems employed for the over-production of proteins, bacteria still remain the favorite choice of a Protein Biochemist. Various researchers have used many techniques to increase the efficiency of the protein production of their choice, some using temperature, volume, nutrient medium and many other factors. Our team decided to go down a different path to test the effect of sound vibrations on Escherichia coli. The impact of sound on biological systems is a subject that has been previously explored, mainly in relation to its use to increase agricultural production, however, the difference in our experiment is the addition of a sound inducible promoter in a plasmid, specifically to increase production of recombinant protein using synthetic biology techniques and to study the direct impact of various frequencies, amplitudes, durations, intermittences and pulses - individually and in combination on the Escherichia coli DH5- α strain. To prove this, we have also designed a sound-proof box that is incubator-friendly, to allow the proper analysis of the effect of sound on bacterial systems. The integral nature of this study presents a deeper understanding of bacterial systems and also offers a way through which it is possible to explore its application for industrial purposes.

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